

The digital divide in light of sustainable development: An approach through advanced machine learning techniques

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ABSTRACT

The growing use of ICT in the workplace has meant that the labor market demands new skills and digital capabilities, either in the production of goods and services or in the need for workers with complementary skills. Concerns about unequal access to new technologies, integrated within the concept of digital divide, has been a topic of study since the use of the Internet began to be generalized among the population. Traditionally, research into the inequalities arising from the emergence of digital technologies has incorporated socioeconomic variables, especially gender, age, educational level, income, and habitat. This study uses advanced data analysis techniques to analyze the main socioeconomic digital skills drivers of the Spanish population. This information allows us to identify whether the population has training needs in relation to their digital competences, which will have a positive influence on improving the level of sustainable development of the country.

Keywords:

Digital skills, Sustainable development, ICT, Advanced machine learning techniques

1. Introduction

The first concerns about sustainability were raised in the 1970s via the Rome Club (Sakalauskas, 2010). However, it was not until 2015 that 193 countries agreed on the 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) proposed by United Nations (Melnikas, 2010). While the setting of these goals is undoubtedly an important milestone, it also represents the first step on a long journey. Recent reports warn of the rise of global wealth inequality – as the richest 1 percent of the world's population owns 88 percent of the world's wealth (Credit Suisse, 2017) – as well as about the increasing rates of unemployment in countries like Spain and Greece, despite their positive GDP evolution.

Although concerns about the unequal access of the population to new technologies has been studied since the use of the Internet began to generalize among the population (Compaine, 2001), the current figures of unemployment and economic inequality in most countries call for a deeper analysis. This can be conceptualized as the “digital divide”, which is defined as the unequal access to and use of information and communication technologies (ICT) (Castells, 2002). This concept has changed over time, from focusing on connectivity (first level of digital divide) to worrying about the development of skills and abilities required to use ICT (second level of digital divide), and measuring the tangible results of the use of the Internet (third level of digital divide) (Scheerder et al., 2017).

The digital divide can be most important when assessing the following sustainable development goals (SDGs): #4 (quality education), #10 (reduced inequalities), and #12 (responsible production and consumption). First, the access to and use of ICT allows for the implementation of new, more effective educational techniques. Second, access to white collar employment is now dependent on the information literacy of individuals. Last, an informed consumer society can foster sustainable production through consumer demand for certain sustainable goods over other less sustainable goods.

Research concerned with the inequalities due to the emergence of digital technologies traditionally incorporated socioeconomic variables into its analysis. In this vein, evidence of the influence of factors such as age, educational level, and employment status in the use and capabilities on the Internet has been proved (van Deursen and van Dijk, 2014; Blank and Grosej, 2014). According to the OECD (2016), the labor market demands new skills and digital capabilities as a result of the growing use of ICT in the workplace, either in the production of ICT goods and services or the need for workers with generic or complementary ICT skills (such as the management of social media or e-commerce platforms). The analysis of inequalities in the digital skills of the population and the determinants of Internet skills, uses, and results has been sought after recently (van Deursen, van Dijk, and Peters, 2015). For this reason, it is crucial for policy makers to identify whether a country's population has training needs related to their digital

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competences (van Deursen, van Dijk and Peters, 2011). The research question that the present article aims to answer is: Which socio-economic variables influence the digital capabilities of the population?

Accordingly, the main goal of this paper is to analyze the digital skills of the Spanish population moderated by their socioeconomic factors. In order to analyze the digital capabilities of the Spanish population, we use the definition of skills, occupations and professional profiles provided recently by the European Commission, aiming for a new framework and set of standards (Fernández Sanz et al., 2016). We opted to focus on the whole population, rather than limiting to the active population, as done by the OECD's online education and skills assessment tool (OECD, 2013) and as proposed in previous studies (CEN, 2014; European Commission, 2015a, 2015b, 2016).

To fulfill the objective of this study, the research approach uses an innovative data analysis methodology based on an artificial intelligence technique: classification and regression trees. This novel technique is able to create an accurate classification of the main digital divide predictors and also offers new and valuable information about the relative importance of each analyzed socioeconomic factor. Furthermore, we explore the possibility of creating a model capable of predicting the digital divide with high accuracy based on the digital skills level of the population, instead of measuring only ICT adoption.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. A literature review is carried out in Section 2 to explain the basis of the digital divide. Section 3 presents the research methodology, and Section 4 summarizes the results and discusses the main findings. Section 5 presents our conclusions.

2. Digital skills: a literature review

Having acquired the motivation to use computers and some kind of physical access to them, individuals must learn to manage the technologies. Digital skills comprise the competencies of individuals that allow them to take advantage of the use of new technologies. Because these competences are not present in the same way among all the population, this concept is integrated into the analysis of the digital divide (second level), which refers to the differences between individuals, households, and firms to the access and use of ICT.

This paper focuses on the digital divide due to the development of skills required to use ICT and the influence of the socioeconomic variables. This approach has been studied by different authors in the last decade using two types of methodology: regression models/structural equations and classification techniques. Both models make it possible to identify the relationships between the use of ICT and a set of socioeconomic variables and understand which variables are the most relevant in that relationship. However, classification techniques have a greater level of accuracy in prediction.

2.1. Regression models/structural equations

The first aspect that stands out when reviewing the state of the art of ICT adoption is the variety of existing approaches when defining digital skills, their uses, and categories. Blank and Groselj (2014) distinguished three minimum dimensions with which to analyze the use of Internet: (i) quantity, (ii) variety, and (iii) types (entertainment, commerce, information search, socialization, email, blog, production, mass media classics, school and work, content for adults). Through standardized regression coefficients, they concluded that age and education have a great influence on the variety and quantity of uses, noting that the Internet users with the greatest number of uses are young people who have the highest level of education.

On the other hand, Hatlevik, Guðmundsdóttir and Loi (2015) identified inequalities in the digital competences of young elementary students. Students responded to self-assessed surveys that incorporated items on cultural capital, language integration, their agreement with a focus of participatory learning, and the academic results obtained in the

semester prior to the interview. They demonstrated, through a model of structural equations, that the digital competences of young students are conditioned by their home, the integration of language and cultural capital, together with the conditioning of the family and the academic marks as the most determining factors.

Hargittai (2010) elaborated on finding differences in Internet skills and uses and the factors that explain them. His approach was to isolate the variables age and level of studies in order to analyze the skills and Internet use of young first year college students (97 percent of the sample was aged 18 or 19). By applying a multiple regression, Hargittai concluded that young students with low socioeconomic status, females, and Hispanic and African American origin presented lower levels of knowledge and Internet use, showing lower skills and variety of use.

Castaño Muñoz, Duart and Sancho Vinuesa (2014) analyzed the use of the Internet for interactive learning, identifying both motivational and perception variables. Through the use of three multiple regression models, the authors showed how young individuals who perceive greater utility in accessing the Internet for interactive learning are those who use it more frequently. Motivation also plays a relevant role in the use of the Internet to carry out interactive actions, with younger students being the most integrated in this use of the Internet. In addition, older students find greater use by women, a difference that would not have been perceived among the younger students; this reflects a convergence of uses and, therefore, a reduction of the digital gender gap between generations. This last evidence was also revealed in relation to the uses of the Internet for non-academic purposes.

Of special interest is the analysis of digital competences through their categorization, which makes it possible to establish more specific guidelines. In this context, van Deursen and van Dijk (2010) distinguished four digital skills according to their purposes: operational capabilities (derived from concepts that indicate a set of basic capabilities in the use of the Internet), formal capabilities (related to the correct use of the Internet and the management of the different connections between web resources: search engines, images, pages, links), information capabilities (related to the development of an information search strategy), and strategic capabilities (necessary to use the Internet according to specific objectives, achieving a general improvement for life). Using two linear regressions, van Deursen and van Dijk concluded that the differences corresponding to the first digital divide (Internet connection, computer availability) were derived from the inequalities in digital skills that correspond to the second digital divide, and that both are strongly related to the level of education. Age is an important factor for understanding the variation in operational and formal capacities, although it is not relevant for information and strategic capacities.

In a later study, van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) delved into the second digital divide by studying the use of the Internet and the differences according to socioeconomic profiles related to these uses. Internet activities were grouped into a set of seven representative activities: information, news, personal development, social interaction, leisure, commercial transactions, and online games. Through a multiple linear regression, they concluded that respondents with low educational level use the Internet in their free time for longer periods of time and mainly for information activities, online games, and social interaction. Unemployed people are more commonly related to the use of the Internet for games and social interaction than employed people, while students are more related to the search for information, personal development, social interaction, and leisure than employed people. The same difference applied according to the habitat: people who live in urban areas make greater use of the Internet for social interaction than those who live in rural areas.

2.2. Classification techniques

Fewer studies in this area use classification techniques. Among them, Kovačić and Vukmirović (2008) compared the results of the

logistic regression and the classification trees techniques to analyze the individual level of ICT adoption (computers, Internet, and mobile phones), determining that ICT adoption was mainly influenced by income, computer and Internet skills, and age. They preferred the classification trees technique because it outperforms the logistic regression with a more parsimonious model. Specifically, about half as many variables were included in the classification tree model as in the logistic regression model. Therefore, the classification tree model is recommended for the classification of an individual as an ICT adopter or non adopter.

Similarly, Coria et al. (2013) used a technique derived from the C4.5 algorithm to describe similarities and differences among a series of municipality classes that present different percentages of presence of Internet in households. This analysis of Internet presence generated some classification rules describing profiles of digital divide of cities.

In the present paper, we integrate the methodology of the classification trees technique to study the digital divide from the point of view of the digital skills of the population (second level) and the output could be taken into account for policy makers for the definition of adequate programs.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Sample and global index of digital skills

The sample size of the survey used for this study is over 17,000 people, an even share of whom have and do not have digital skills. The data comes from the digital skills survey conducted in Spain by the Statistics National Institute (INE, 2017) following the methodology of the European Commission regarding the creation of a global index of digital skills (European Commission, 2015 a, 2015b, 2016).

This index includes information on global digital skills for the population and uses information on the following domains: information related skills (includes activities of search, compilation and handling of information, judgment of its relevance and purpose), communication skills (includes competences related to communication in digital environments, such as sharing resources, participating in social networks and collaborating through digital tools), problem solving skills (includes the ability to identify needs and solve them through the appropriate digital tools), and software related skills (qualifies the digital skills of the population according to their competences related to the creation and edition of new contents through digital tools). All of the variables are dichotomous and express the development of different action characteristics of the information society.

The activities included within information skills are copying or moving files or folders, saving files in Internet space, obtaining information from the websites of public administrations, finding information about goods or services, and searching for information related to health. The activities included within communication skills are sending/receiving emails, participating in social networks, making audio calls or video calls over the Internet, and uploading personally created content to a website. For both domains, the categorization of the levels of digital skills was defined as follows: none (if the user did not perform any of the actions described), basic (if the user performed one of the described actions), and higher than basic (if the user performed several of the described actions).

The calculation of problem solving skills and software related skills domains in the present study is different from that used in previous studies. In this case, the variables used differ in two groups according to the difficulty of the digital activity (Group A = easier; Group B = greater difficulty), with the difference being the importance that each group will have for the categorization of the levels. The activities included within both domains are reflected in Tables 1 and 2. In order to calculate the competence level categories of these domains, the following conditions were taken into account: none (if none of the actions described were performed), basic (at least one activity from Group A

Table 1
Activities included in problem-solving skills.
Source: European Commission (2016).

A	B
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer files between PCs and devices • Install software and applications • Change settings of some software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make on-line purchases (last 12 months) • Make on-line sales • Use on-line educational resources • Use on-line banking

Table 2
Activities included in software-related skills.
Source: European Commission (2016).

A	B
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of word processor (Word) • Use of spreadsheets • Use of photo, video, or audio file editor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create presentations or document with text images, tables or graphics • Use of advanced spreadsheet functions • Write codes in programming language

was performed, but none from Group B) and higher than basic (at least one activity was carried out from each of Groups A and B).

Using this information, the global index of digital skills was created by taking into account the following conditions: none (did not perform any of the activities described for the different domains of digital capabilities), low (no activity in between one and three domains of digital capabilities), basic (any of the activities in each domain of digital capabilities was performed, but at least a basic use in one of them) and superior (higher than basic use in all domains). For the analysis, we grouped the categories none and low, on the one hand, and basic and superior, on the other, which classifies the population with no digital skills or with very low skills level, and the population with basic or superior digital skills level.

3.2. Methodology

To analyze and assess the most relevant socioeconomic variables that impact on the digital skills of the population and cause the digital skills divide in Spain, we implemented a classification tree data mining technique. This is a machine learning predictive technique, derived from the decision tree models, that works as a recursive data partitioning process by maximizing the internal homogeneity of the classification tree nodes. This classification technique analyses each possible grouping of values as two different data partitions or splits. For each of the combinations or groupings tested, the algorithm evaluates the impurity of the child nodes for the split based on that grouping. This approach goes beyond using the predictive capabilities of the classification trees technique to assess the role of each relevant socioeconomic driver for the digital skills of the population, and creating a prediction for a new sample using the machine learning model built in the process.

The use of machine learning decision tree models for the research offers several advantages for the analysis, the results, and assessment of the relevance of the various socioeconomic factors used (Singh and Gupta, 2014; Sharma and Kumar, 2016; Painsky and Rosset, 2017). This technique can work with numeric and categorical variables, handle missing values and outliers in the training data, and tree performance is not affected by non linear relationships between variables. Moreover, unlike other machine learning methods such as the artificial neural networks or the support vector machines, the resulting decision tree models offer a representation of the variable relationships that is both intuitive and easy to understand, because the construction of the classification tree is a self explanatory process.

For the classification tree analysis, the main dependent variable that we selected for the study was the digital skills levels of the population,

Table. 3
Socioeconomic factors evaluated.

Variable	Variable categories
Gender	Male or female
Age (years)	16 24, 25 34, 35 44, 45 54, 55 64 or >64 years old.
Education level	Illiterate, primary, first secondary stage, second secondary stage, vocational training, or university.
Occupation	Student, employed, unemployed, homemaker, retired, or other.
Household income (monthly)	Less than €900; €900 1600 euros; €1601 2500; €2501 3000, or more than €3000.
Habitat (number of inhabitants)	<10,000; 10,000 20,000; 20,001 50,000; 50,001 100,000; 100,001 500,000; >500,000 inhabitants.

which we divided into two main groups: no skills or low skills, and basic and above skills. The socioeconomic factors evaluated (in dependent variables of the tree model) and their corresponding levels are shown in Table 3.

The impurity index is used to measure the accuracy of a given node representing a subset of homogeneous data (Gulati et al., 2016). A purely homogenous node in the classification tree would be a node in which all the cases have the same value of the objective (dependent) variable; for example, all the cases with basic or high skills. This type of node would not need additional divisions, as it would be considered as a pure node. The technique automatically chooses the optimal split point for the predicted value as the one that leads to a larger impurity reduction, taking into account the starting impurity index of the node that is divided.

In this research, the impurity index measure used for the classification tree technique is the Gini index. This approach yields split points that maximize the homogeneity of the child nodes with respect to the objective variable. The measure used in the Gini index is related to the square of the probability of pertaining to each of the dependent variable categories. A value of 0 in the Gini index (the minimum possible value) is obtained when all the cases in one node correspond to only one of the objective variable categories. The tree model stopping rule for the tree growing algorithm is a minimum impurity index improvement change of 0.001. Also, the maximum allowed tree depth is five levels, which enhances the interpretation of results and avoids possible less relevant tree nodes.

In order to prevent the classification tree over fitting, we also implemented a decision tree pruning technique in which the maximum acceptable difference in risk between the pruned tree and the sub tree with a lower risk is one standard error. Additionally, the research has validated the predictive accuracy of the classification tree using training and testing samples. For this procedure, we divided the initial sample of over 17,000 cases randomly selected in the survey into two random subsamples: the training sample contains 70 percent of the cases, and the testing sample contains the other 30 percent. This testing and validation approach makes it possible to evaluate the model's prediction accuracy.

4. Main findings

The prediction accuracy of the classification tree model is 79.9 percent for the training sample and 80.7 percent for the testing sample. These figures are especially interesting in the case of the prediction for the higher digital skills group (close to 85 percent). According to these results, the model risk estimate is 0.2, with a standard error of 0.005 (Table 4), which reflects the high general accuracy of the predictive classification tree model using new data (for testing).

Fig. 1 contains the tree model structure in which the relevant information of the training classification model results is presented. Each node contains both graphical and numerical (relative and absolute) information about the distribution of the objective variable in two levels (digital skills). In the node 0, at the top of the decision tree model, the distribution of the cases of the training sample (70 percent of the total survey sample) is close to 50 percent for each of the predicted digital skills categories.

Table. 4
Classification accuracy table.

Sample		Predicted No/low skills	Basic/above	Percent correct
Training	No/low skills	4480	1494	75.0%
	Basic/above	884	4982	84.9%
	Overall percentage	45.3%	54.7%	79.9%
Testing	No/low skills	1893	600	75.9%
	Basic/above	369	2153	85.4%
	Overall percentage	45.1%	54.9%	80.7%

The first level of the tree is divided by the first independent variable: the education level. The improvement in the impurity index gained at this first tree level is 0.130. The education level threshold that splits the sample in the two first groups of cases is the secondary education level. In this level (node 1) we observe that 77.8 percent of the cases with education level corresponding to the first secondary stage (primary or illiterate cases) have no or a low level of digital skills, compared to 22.2 percent of the population with this education level who have basic or above basic digital skills. This result contrasts with the digital skills level of the population with higher education levels (university, vocational training and secondary education), for which 73.3 percent have basic or above digital skills level, compared to 26.7 percent with low or no digital skills levels (node 2).

Progressing down to the tree branch of the lower education levels (node 1), the age of the person also plays a relevant role determining the digital skills, with an impurity index improvement of 0.033. The split threshold for the second level of the tree for this branch (nodes 3 and 4) is the age of 45 years. Thus, 90.6 percent of the sample with lower studies and an age above 44 have low or no digital skills (node 3). In the population with lower education level but aged less than 45, the proportion of digital skills levels is close to the 50 percent for each level (node 4). This shows the effect of the age on the lower education group regarding digital skills distribution.

Descending from node 2, we find another relevant factor for the configuration of the digital skills level: occupation (impurity index improvement of 0.018). At this level – the population group with education level of secondary education, vocational training and university (node 2) – the results show that the retired (over 65 years old) and homemaker groups (node 5) have, on average, a lower proportion of basic and above digital skills (40.9 percent). Meanwhile, the other occupations, such as employed, unemployed, and students (node 6) present a much higher skills level (78.5 percent). This result shows that despite the higher education of these two groups, age and occupation also play a role in the conformation of the digital skills of the population.

Among this group of retired people and homemakers with higher education attainment (node 5), progressing down the tree structure, we observe that the household monthly income is also a relevant factor (impurity index improvement of 0.003). When monthly income is over 2500 euros (node 9), people generally present a higher proportion of basic and above digital skills (68.2 percent). If income is lower than this threshold (node 10), the digital skills level is lower (34.1 percent of basic or above skills).

Fig.. 1. Training classification tree model.

Continuing down the tree structure from the node 4, for the population with lower education attainment and younger than 45 years old, occupation again plays a significant splitting role at the situation of the younger students (node 8), with a proportion of basic and above skills of 83.7 percent. For the rest of the groups (retired, employed, un employed, and homemaker), digital skills are much lower, with only 39.8 percent having basic and above digital skills (node 7).

At the fourth tree level from node 7, the worst digital skills situation

is reflected by the cases with primary or no studies (node 11), with a basic and above skills level proportion of 17 percent (basically, the opposite situation to the younger students group reflected in node 8). The cases of node 12, with secondary education level, are more evenly distributed between the two skills levels groups. Finally, at the fifth level of the tree structure, age again plays a discriminant role and in the 35 – 44 age group (node 13), 59.1 percent of cases have no or low digital skills; this contrasts to the younger age groups (less than 35 years),

Fig.. 2. Relative importance of socioeconomic factors for the digital skills level prediction.

in which the proportion of cases with no or low skills is 44.7 percent (node 14).

Bearing in mind that the objective of the research is to evaluate what drivers could improve the digital divide among the Spanish population and the extent to which digital skills can be predicted using solely common socioeconomic variables, the results of the tree modeling process show that the main socioeconomic drivers affecting the digital skills level of the population are age, education level, and occupation (Fig. 2).

5. Conclusions

The digital divide is increasingly influencing socioeconomic inequalities and job opportunities around the world. Digital inequality could lead to economic inequality, particularly for younger people, who could be excluded from the labor market and lack the education opportunities to access to an increasingly digitalized business world. This fact will undoubtedly have an important impact on the level of sustainable development of a country. In this context, the EU recently adopted the new Digital Europe Program for 2021 – 2027, which proposes the necessary acquisition of digital skills by EU citizens to ensure that the current and future workforce can easily acquire advanced digital skills, notably in high performance computing, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity, by offering students, graduates, and existing workers the means to acquire and develop these skills regardless of where they are situated.

The literature review shows that there are different categorizations of digital capabilities, as well as different methodologies through which to address the object of study. The digital skills differences detected in several studies also affect the socioeconomic polarization, creating a divide between broad segments of the population that, if not addressed adequately and promptly, would increase the digital divide and its pernicious effects on wide population groups, which could be excluded from the benefits of the information and communication digital revolution and Industry 4.0 advantages and opportunities. Additionally, a population with a higher digital skills level could also constitute a catalyst increasing the innovative potential of countries and businesses and their global competitiveness. Therefore, understanding its underlying factors and social conditionals is crucial in order to ensure a reduction of the current and future socioeconomic and job inequalities

related to digital skills.

The primary contribution of this paper is in explaining the main socioeconomic factors that explain the digital skills divide using advanced machine learning techniques, such as the classification trees technique. The application of this technique to the study of the Spanish population yielded a series of relevant findings. The results show that the machine learning algorithm selected variables such as education level, age, occupation, and household income as key predictors to the digital skills of the population, creating a digital skills divide between different population groups. The younger population groups, especially students, also tend to be more digitally skilled, and occupations that are relatively less digitally skilled are retirees and homemakers, especially in lower income households. We must also highlight the persistence of inequalities in the incorporation and use of ICT. Although the digital divide is reduced both in the physical incorporation of technology and in terms of digital capabilities and incorporation of some generalist uses (search for information, video calls over the Internet, etc.), inequality becomes visible as soon as they link the uses with social groups and the results obtained.

This information is very useful for understanding the reality of the information society in Spain and the integration of its population therein. The findings of this research could be used by policy makers to design specific action programs oriented to reduce the digital divide among the Spanish population and foster policies aimed at favoring digital inclusion in the information society. These policies should incorporate the digital competences that, according to the [World Economic Forum \(2016\)](#), citizens must have in order to be able to work with dexterity in the digital environment. These competences include digital identity (managing identity and online reputation), digital rights (privacy, intellectual property, freedom of expression and protection of expressions against hate), literacy (using, sharing and creating digital content), communication (collaborating with other people who use technologies and digital media), emotional intelligence (building relationships with others online), prevention (detecting computer threats such as hacking, scams, malicious software, to understand best practices and use the appropriate security tools), security (managing online risks such as cyber bullying and radicalization, and problematic content such as violence and obscenity), and the use of digital devices and media, including control of their use. In this context, the goal posed by the [Internet Society \(2015\)](#) would be more reachable

in the sense that the Internet provides the underpinning platform for the growth of ICTs and for an emerging digital economy, in which production, distribution and consumption depend on broadband networks and services. It will, therefore, be a critical enabler of sustainable development.

As our results demonstrate, the application of artificial intelligence approaches to the analysis of complex socioeconomic problems can offer new and interesting information from an academic point of view. The research method could also be applied to build machine learning predictive models to shed new light on other areas related to sustainable development, such as the origin or the main drivers of other social factors like economic and financial culture or professional activity.

As next steps, we would consider the extrapolation of the machine learning predictive technique to a wider group of EU or OECD countries to evaluate possible divergences and similarities in the digital skills among different countries and to evaluate whether the socioeconomic factors detected in the Spanish population remain the same in other countries. Another line of research would be oriented to analyze the employability of the active population based on the digital skills level to assess the economic inequalities.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119754](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119754).

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